

Original Research

Determinants of Financial Governance with Risk-Based Audit as a Moderating Variable at Community Health Centers Across Lombok Island

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze and provide empirical evidence regarding the influence of locus of control, information systems, and compliance on financial governance, as well as the influence of locus of control, information systems, and compliance moderated by risk-based audit on financial governance. The population of this study consists of all community health centers (Puskemas) across Lombok Island, totaling 506 units. Data were collected through a survey using a questionnaire. By applying the purposive sampling method, the study involved 477 respondents. The data analysis method used in this study was Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with the assistance of Smart PLS version 3.0 software. The results of the study indicate that the locus of control variable has a positive and significant effect on financial governance; the management information system also has a positive and significant effect on financial governance; compliance has no effect on financial governance; risk-based audit does not moderate the influence of locus of control on financial governance; risk-based audit does not moderate the influence of management information systems on financial governance; and risk-based audit does not moderate the influence of compliance on financial governance.

Keywords: Compliance, Financial Governance, Locus of Control, Management Information System, Risk-Based Audit.

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Introduction

One way to achieve organizational goals is by implementing effective supervision or internal control systems to minimize potential deviations. Enhancing the role of internal audit is crucial in assisting the management of risks that may threaten the achievement of organizational objectives (Coetzee, 2010).

A risk-oriented approach is currently considered the most appropriate method to fulfill the objectives set by a company's internal audit services (Harna, 2019). Risk-based auditing is an examination methodology used to provide assurance that existing risks have been properly managed and that management-established limits do not negatively affect the organization's objectives.

From an internal perspective, management has a better understanding of the priority risks that may arise and how to address them efficiently and effectively, thereby reducing the likelihood of errors in the audit process. According to the Institute of Internal Auditors, "*Internal auditing is an independent, objective assurance and consulting activity designed to add value and improve an organization's operations.*" In planning each audit engagement, the application of a risk-based approach is positively correlated with the size of the entity (Castanheira et al., 2010). Internal audits are conducted across all types of organizations, including those in the health sector such as community health centers (Puskesmas)

The Indonesia Corruption Watch (ICW) discovered several potential fraud practices committed by participants of the National Health Insurance (JKN) program, healthcare providers, and the organizing body, namely the Social Security Administration Agency for Health (BPJS Kesehatan). The fraudulent practices identified were quite complex, including issues such as invalid and inaccurate data collection. In 2017, ICW found that many participants who were not eligible to receive Premium Assistance Beneficiary (PBI) status were still able to use PBI benefits, and vice versa.

Furthermore, based on ICW's 2017 monitoring of 26 community health centers (Puskesmas) across 14 provinces, potential fraud was also found in the management of capitation funds. The findings included: 1) The use of capitation funds that did not comply with the provisions of laws and regulations (2 cases); 2) Manipulation of accountability reports and the disbursement of capitation funds (1 case); and 3) Charging fees to participants who should have been fully covered under the capitation and/or non-capitation cost standards (5 cases).

In 2019, fraudulent practices were also found in the area of drug management. This was revealed through research conducted in four cities—Banda Aceh, Medan, Banten, and Blitar. The causes of drug shortages in these four cities included delays in drug distribution by pharmaceutical companies, inaccuracies in the preparation of Drug Requirement Plans (RKO), and outstanding debts from healthcare facilities (faskes).

In early February 2018, a sting operation (OTT) carried out by the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) against the Regent of Jombang exposed issues related to the management of capitation funds. The operation revealed that the Acting Head of the

District Health Office (Kadinkes) had collected portions of capitation funds from 34 community health centers (Puskesmas) in Jombang Regency and used them to provide illicit payments to the Regent of Jombang.

Corruption cases handled by law enforcement agencies involving the management of capitation funds during the 2014–2018 period showed similar patterns. There were eight corruption cases related to the management of Puskesmas capitation funds across eight regions, causing state losses of approximately Rp 5.8 billion, with 14 individuals named as suspects.

The corruption of capitation funds did not occur only in Jombang Regency but also in other regions. One such case took place in the city of Mataram, involving two defendants, former Head of Babakan Community Health Center (Puskesmas), Raden Heindra, and former treasurer Ni Wayan Yuniarti, who were convicted of embezzling capitation funds from Babakan Puskesmas in Mataram during 2017–2019. According to the calculation of the Audit Board for Finance and Development (BPKP) Representative of West Nusa Tenggara (NTB), the state suffered a financial loss of Rp 690 million. Defendant Raden Heindra, as the head of Babakan Puskesmas, was found to have taken loans from the capitation fund. In addition, both defendants, Heindra and Yuniarti, who served as treasurer, were found to have made unauthorized deductions during the disbursement process of the capitation funds.

From these issues, financial governance has become one of the key elements in managing Puskesmas funds to ensure public accountability in government administration and to bridge the gap between the government and society (Mendrofa et al., 2020). To achieve accountable financial governance, it is essential to have adequate human resource capabilities, particularly in terms of locus of control, which reflects an individual's belief in their ability to control the factors that influence them (Kuncoro, 2017). Furthermore, it is necessary to establish a management information system that promotes financial transparency through the use of information technology in managing Puskesmas funds. In addition, increasing individual awareness and compliance with applicable laws and regulations is also crucial.

In addition, it is important to emphasize the significance of risk-based audit planning in minimizing potential risks. During the auditing process, auditors must consider audit planning and the design of audit procedures in order to obtain competent audit evidence (Zakiah, 2017a). The implementation of a risk-based audit can assist in effectively fulfilling management's responsibilities. Conceptually, a risk-based audit is closely related to organizational risk management. Specifically, a risk-based audit aims to evaluate the effectiveness of an organization's risk management in handling potential risks through monitoring and review processes designed to ensure that risk management implementation aligns with established plans and serves as a foundation for continuous improvement of risk management processes. By implementing risk-based auditing, organizations can realize sound financial governance.

Several previous studies have attempted to analyze the factors influencing governance, particularly in relation to financial governance. Research by Mawanza et al., (2018) found that banks in Zimbabwe demonstrated a high level of compliance with corporate

governance principles. Furthermore, a study by Shanti et al., (2020) concluded that the implementation of Integrated Reporting (IR) has a positive impact on corporate governance within ASEAN capital markets, as IR adoption encourages behavioral and perceptual changes in corporate governance, thereby making governance practices more effective.

Previous studies discussing the determinants of financial governance with risk-based audit as a moderating variable include research by (Gusman & Auliffi, 2023), which examined The Influence of Remote Auditing, Computer-Assisted Audit Techniques, Auditor Performance, and Locus of Control on Audit Quality. The findings showed that remote auditing and computer-assisted audit techniques had no significant effect on audit quality, while auditor performance and locus of control had a positive and significant effect on audit quality.

Another study conducted by Syam et al., (2023) titled Risk-Based Audit on Internal Audit Activities and Risk Management of Hospitals in Makassar revealed that the risk-based audit variable had a significant effect on internal audit activities, a significant effect on risk management, and a significant indirect effect on risk management through internal audit activities.

Furthermore, Shanti (2020) in her study titled Integrated Reporting's (IR) Impact on Corporate Governance: A Study in ASEAN Capital Markets found, using Stata 14.2 statistical analysis, that the implementation of Integrated Reporting (IR) had a positive impact on corporate governance in ASEAN capital markets. The study concluded that IR implementation encourages behavioral and perceptual changes in corporate governance (behavior driven by reporting), thereby making governance practices more effective.

Additionally, Harna (2019) in a study titled Risk-Based Approach in Internal Audit found that the foundation of a risk-oriented approach in internal auditing lies in the processes of risk identification and assessment and in the effectiveness of risk management. Accurate understanding of the essence of a risk-oriented approach should be considered when developing internal audit plans and programs, as it influences the selection and verification of audit objectives.

Another study was conducted by Mwanza et al., (2018) titled Corporate Governance Compliance Model: The Extent to Which Financial Institutions Have Complied with the Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe (RBZ) Corporate Governance Guideline No. 01-2004/BSD of 2004. The results showed that 20% of financial institutions did not comply with the RBZ Corporate Governance (CG) guideline regarding board meetings. The findings also revealed that the composition of bank boards listed on the Zimbabwe Stock Exchange (ZSE) complied with the RBZ guideline, which requires that each banking institution have at least five directors and no more than five directors studied. The study concluded that banks in Zimbabwe have a high level of compliance with CG principles in areas such as board composition, risk management, remuneration, audit committees, and codes of ethics. It was recommended that the Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe continue to supervise banks regarding CG guideline requirements and best practices to prevent bank failures and stabilize the financial sector.

Another study by Baker & Garland E. Allen (2013) titled *Restraining Regulatory Capture? Anglo-America, Crisis Politics, and Trajectories of Change in Global Financial Governance* examined the extent to which reform efforts have achieved their goals in the current global financial governance framework. The study highlighted persistent challenges that continue to hinder efforts to restrict regulatory capture. Evidence regarding the effectiveness of regulatory restraint remains mixed, and when it occurs, it is often both intentional and unintentional. Recent reforms, however, have tended to overlook the political causes of the crisis and have failed to focus explicitly or systematically on regulatory issues.

The study by Indrawati (2013) titled *Principles of Good Financial Governance in State Financial Management to Achieve Clean Governance* showed that the sustainability of Indonesia's development essentially depends on the management of the State Budget (APBN). Ideal state financial management is based on the principles of good governance (which has now become a dynamic pattern of state administration worldwide toward democratic stability) in harmony with the principles of good financial governance. The implementation of good financial governance principles in laws and regulations related to state financial management can help realize clean governance. As an implementation of the principles of legality and legal certainty, the imposition of sanctions for deviations in state financial management must be based on applicable laws and regulations while upholding respect for human rights.

The study by Castanheira et al. (2010) titled *Factors Associated with the Adoption of Risk-Based Internal Auditing* aimed to analyze specific company factors associated with the adoption of risk-based auditing. The study sought to explore the role of internal auditing in Enterprise Risk Management (ERM). A questionnaire survey was conducted in 2006, distributed to 96 chief internal auditors who were members of the Portuguese Institute of Internal Auditors. The results showed that when planning the annual audit schedule, the adoption of a risk-based approach was statistically significant in international companies ($p \leq 0.05$) and companies listed on the Portuguese stock market ($p \leq 0.10$). A strong (though not significant) relationship was found between risk-based annual audit planning and private entities, the financial sector, and large companies. In planning each audit engagement, the adoption of a risk-based approach correlated positively with entity size. Internal auditing was more proactive in the implementation of ERM in smaller organizations, particularly in the financial industry and private sector.

The study by Coetzee (2010) titled *A Risk-Based Audit Model for Internal Audit Engagements* examined the evolution of the internal auditing profession along with the concepts of corporate governance, risk management, and the role of internal audit. This study specifically focused on how internal auditors can incorporate risk into the execution of internal audit engagements to enhance their effectiveness and efficiency. A review of these topics and the initial model of risk-based internal audit engagement was developed based on existing literature.

Subsequently, organizations from both the private and public sectors in South Africa were assessed using a risk maturity scorecard to determine which organizations had achieved maturity in risk management. The five most mature organizational risks from each sector were included in the second empirical study, with the main objective of

gathering input from chief audit executives (CAEs) to refine the initial risk-based engagement model. Finally, the model was tested in a practical scenario using a case study approach to determine whether improvements in the execution of internal audit engagements were possible. The results of the three empirical studies were then integrated to finalize the model.

Based on the previous studies, the current researcher is interested in examining the influence of locus of control, management information systems, and compliance on financial governance, with risk-based auditing serving as a moderating variable. The emphasis in risk-based auditing lies in strengthening audit engagement by enhancing the understanding of risks that must be anticipated, managed, or mitigated by management in order to achieve organizational objectives (Ardiana & Aini, 2022).

The novelty of this study lies in the use of different constructs from prior research, aiming to contribute to the development of scientific knowledge, particularly in the field of public sector accounting. This study uses risk-based auditing as a moderating variable between locus of control, management information systems, and compliance toward financial governance. Furthermore, the selection of a distinct research object — specifically public health centers (Puskesmas) throughout Lombok Island, West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) — is based on the relatively high number of irregularities in the allocation of capitation funds, thus necessitating further research to obtain empirical evidence.

Most previous studies have not yet linked the implementation of risk-based auditing with financial governance. This gap has motivated the researcher to examine the relationship between locus of control, management information systems, and compliance with financial governance, moderated by the implementation of risk-based auditing.

Based on these phenomena and previous studies, this research aims to analyze and provide empirical evidence regarding: The effect of locus of control on financial governance; The effect of management information systems on financial governance; The effect of compliance on financial governance; The effect of locus of control on financial governance as moderated by risk-based auditing; The effect of management information systems on financial governance as moderated by risk-based auditing; and The effect of compliance on financial governance as moderated by risk-based auditing.

Literature Review

Robbins & Judge (2018: 138) define Locus of Control as the degree to which individuals believe they are the masters of their own destiny. As stated by Soepriadi et al., (2015) , Locus of Control refers to an individual's control over their work and their perception of their own success. According to Kuncoro (2017), Locus of Control indicates a person's belief in their ability to control factors that can influence themselves.

An individual is considered to have an internal locus of control when they believe that the outcomes of their work are influenced by their own abilities, skills, and efforts. Conversely, when an individual or auditor perceives that the results of their work are

largely determined by external factors beyond their control, the auditor is categorized as having an external locus of control (Prameisti & Rasmini, 2016).

A Management Information System (MIS) is a system designed to assist management in collecting, processing, and analyzing data, as well as evaluating and presenting valuable information for decision-making. Davis defines a Management Information System as an integrated human/machine system that provides information to support the operational functions of management and decision-making within an organization. In essence, a Management Information System is an integrated system that delivers information to support financial management operations and decision-making processes within an organization.

Compliance is a phenomenon similar to self-adjustment. The difference lies in the aspect of legitimate influence (as opposed to coercion or social pressure) and the consistent presence of an individual who holds authority. Obedience (compliance) is defined as a disciplined attitude or behavior of adherence to a command or rule established with full awareness. Compliance, as a form of positive behavior, is considered a choice, meaning that individuals consciously choose to act, obey, and respond critically to rules, laws, social norms, requests, or the desires of someone in a position of authority or influence.

Feildman, as cited in Septi Kusumadewi, defines compliance as “change behavior in response to the command of others”, which refers to a change in an individual’s behavior or attitude in response to the requests or commands of others. Compliance can occur in any form, as long as the individual demonstrates obedient behavior toward something or someone.

Regulations are defined as orders, guidelines, or provisions concerning what may or may not be done. The purpose of regulations is to direct members of society to create an orderly pattern of life. Obedience to regulations means behaving in accordance with prevailing rules, having an attitude of acceptance and sincerity in carrying out applicable regulations with wholeheartedness and without coercion.

The basic principles of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) formulated by the OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development) consist of five aspects: 1) Transparency, which refers to openness in information, both in decision-making processes and in the disclosure of material and relevant information regarding the organization; 2) Accountability, which involves functions, structures, systems, and responsibilities of corporate organs to ensure effective company management; 3) Responsibility, meaning compliance with sound corporate principles and applicable laws and regulations in corporate management; 4) Independency, which refers to a condition in which management is carried out professionally and free from conflicts of interest; and 5) Fairness, which emphasizes fair and equal treatment in fulfilling the rights of stakeholders arising from agreements and applicable laws and regulations.

According to the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 13 of 2006 concerning Guidelines for Regional Financial Management, Article 4 explains that regional finances must be managed in an orderly manner, in compliance with the

prevailing laws and regulations, and in an effective, efficient, economical, transparent, and accountable way, while upholding the principles of justice, appropriateness, and benefits for the community.

Risk-based auditing is an audit methodology used to provide assurance that risks have been managed within the limits set by management at the corporate level (Ardiana & Aini, 2022). The numerous audit risks that exist are difficult to measure and require careful consideration before auditors can respond appropriately. Therefore, auditing standards require consideration of inherent risk, which refers to the susceptibility of an assertion to a material misstatement, assuming there are no related internal controls; control risk, which refers to the risk that a material misstatement in an assertion will not be prevented or detected in a timely manner by the entity's internal control structure; and detection risk, which refers to the risk that the auditor fails to detect a material misstatement in an assertion. Several previous studies related to Determinants of Financial Governance with Risk-Based Audit as a Moderating Variable at Community Health Centers (Puskesmas) throughout Lombok Island are as follows:

Gusman & Auliffi (2023) conducted a study entitled *The Effect of Remote Auditing, Computer-Assisted Audit Techniques, Auditor Performance, and Locus of Control on Audit Quality*. The results showed that remote auditing and computer-assisted audit techniques had no effect on audit quality, while auditor performance and locus of control had a positive and significant effect on audit quality.

Another study by Syam et al., (2023) entitled *Risk-Based Audit on Internal Audit Activities and Risk Management in Hospitals in Makassar* showed that the risk-based audit variable had a significant effect on internal audit activities, a significant effect on risk management, and a significant indirect effect on risk management through internal audit activities.

A study by (Ardiana & Aini, 2022) entitled *The Effect of Good Governance on Regional Financial Management Transparency in the Regional Working Units of Ponorogo* found that the good governance variable had a positive and significant effect on the transparency of regional financial management in Ponorogo Regency. This means that the better the governance (good governance), the more transparent the regional financial management becomes. The study showed that good governance affected the transparency of regional financial management by 8.6%, while the remaining 91.4% was influenced by other factors not included in the model.

A study by Tuteja & Nagpal, (2013) entitled *Transparency of Local Financial Management: Evidence from Local Governments in Indonesia* showed that regional independence, the human development index, and audit opinions from the Audit Board of Indonesia (BPK) were proven to have a positive effect on improving the transparency of regional financial management in Indonesia. On the other hand, political competition did not affect the improvement of regional financial management transparency in Indonesia.

The study further suggested that future research should consider other factors to obtain more comprehensive results. These factors include the size of local government, regional

expenditure, local government wealth, legislative size, government complexity, level of dependency, local government financial capacity, media visibility, and administrative age of local governments.

These findings contribute to fundamental ideas and recommendations for the government to enhance the transparency of regional financial management in Indonesia.

Based on the theoretical review and previous studies described above, the conceptual framework of this research can be illustrated in Figure 1 as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Methods of Research

This study is a causal associative research employing a survey method, in which data were collected and analyzed based on respondents' answers. The primary data collection instrument used in this research is a questionnaire, which serves as the main tool to gather relevant information according to the research objectives. The research population includes all community health centers (Puskesmas) across the island of Lombok. The total population consists of 506 Puskesmas, comprising 159 main Puskesmas, 189 auxiliary Puskesmas, 35 mobile Puskesmas, and 123 sub-health centers (Poskesdes) throughout Lombok Island.

The sample was selected using the purposive sampling method based on specific criteria. The sampling criterion used in this study was main Puskesmas located in each sub-district. Based on the established criteria, the research sample consisted of 11 Puskesmas in Mataram City, 15 in West Lombok, 28 in Central Lombok, 97 in East Lombok, and 8 in North Lombok, resulting in a total of 159 Puskesmas included in the study. The respondents consisted of heads of Puskesmas, treasurers, and internal auditors, as these parties are considered to have a good understanding of the financial governance conditions in their respective institutions.

The data analysis method employed in this research is Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) using the SmartPLS version 3.0 software.

PLS-SEM aims to test predictive relationships between constructs, determining whether relationships or effects exist among those constructs (Ghozali, 2014:31).

Results and Discussion

From the test results using SmartPLS with the PLS-SEM Algorithm method, the results obtained are shown in Figure 2 as follows:

Figure 2. Loading Factor Values

Based on Figure 2, it can be concluded that the results of the validity test for the variables above show that the loading factor values of the statement items for the Locus of Control (X1) construct are greater than 0.70. The highest loading factor value that meets the validity requirement in the Locus of Control (X1) variable is found in the first statement item (X1.1) with a value of 0.865. However, the statement items X1.2, X1.3, X1.4, and X1.5 in variable X1 have values below 0.70, namely 0.520; 0.597; 0.112; and 0.003, respectively. Therefore, these items must be dropped from the model because they do not meet the validity requirements of the X1 construct.

For the Management Information System (X2) variable, the highest loading factor value is found in item X2.3 with a value of 0.826, while the lowest value that still meets the validity requirement is item X2.5 with a value of 0.711. However, statement items X2.1 and X2.5 in the Management Information System (X2) variable have values below 0.70, namely 0.651 and 0.689, respectively. Thus, these items must also be dropped from the model because they do not meet the construct validity requirements of X2.

For the Compliance (X3) variable, the highest loading factor value is found in item X3.4 with a value of 0.869, while the lowest value that still meets the validity requirement is item X3.2 with a value of 0.763. However, the statement item X3.1 in the Compliance (X3) variable has a value below 0.70, which is 0.637. Therefore, this item must be

dropped from the model as it does not meet the construct validity requirements of the Compliance (X3) variable.

For the Risk-Based Audit (Z) variable, the highest loading factor value is found in item Z4 with a value of 0.774, while the lowest value that still meets the validity requirement is item Z1 with a value of 0.707. However, the statement items Z2, Z3, and Z5 in the Risk-Based Audit (Z) variable have values below 0.70, namely 0.607; 0.619; and 0.681, respectively. Therefore, these items must be dropped from the model because they do not meet the construct validity requirements of the Risk-Based Audit (Z) variable.

Furthermore, for the Financial Governance (Y) variable, the highest loading factor value is found in item Y9 with a value of 0.753, while the lowest value that still meets the validity requirement is item Y6 with a value of 0.705. However, the statement items Y2, Y5, Y7, Y8, and Y10 in the Financial Governance (Y) variable have values below 0.70, namely 0.678; 0.676; 0.699; 0.684; and 0.654, respectively. Therefore, these items must be dropped from the model because they do not meet the construct validity requirements of the Financial Governance (Y) variable.

The re-estimation results after removing the statement items that did not meet the validity requirements can be seen in Table/Figure 3 as follows:

Figure 3. Re-Estimation Loading Factor Values

From Figure 3, it can be seen that the results of the loading factor test for each indicator on their respective variables show that all loading factor values are greater than 0.70. This indicates that each indicator can represent its respective variable in the study.

The next step is to conduct a reliability test, which involves examining the Cronbach's Alpha value (greater than 0.70), Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values (greater than 0.50). Based on the results of the PLS-SEM Algorithm, the values for each variable are as follows:

Table 1. Values of Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
X1	1,000	1,000	1,000
X2	0,816	0,869	0,573
X3	0,789	0,861	0,612
Z	0,688	0,826	0,614
Y	0,823	0,876	0,585

From Table 1, it is known that the Cronbach's Alpha values for each indicator are greater than 0.70. If the Cronbach's Alpha value is greater than 0.90, the reliability is considered perfect; if it is between 0.70 – 0.90, the reliability is high; if it is between 0.50 – 0.70, the reliability is moderate; and if it is less than 0.50, the reliability is low (Murfiyah Mardiani Sanaky et al., 2021). Therefore, it can be concluded that the reliability for variables X1, X2, X3, Z, and Y is high, as the Cronbach's Alpha values fall within the range of 0.70 – 0.90.

Next is the test using the Composite Reliability value. Composite reliability is conducted to assess the consistency of each indicator for every variable. The minimum standard value for composite reliability in research is > 0.70 (Kamajaya Putra Pamungkas et al., 2019). From Table 4.12, it is known that each variable has a value greater than 0.70, meaning that the indicators of each variable can be considered reliable.

The level of convergent validity, which can be seen from the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value, is already greater than 0.50. This indicates that the proportion of variance explained by the indicators for each variable exceeds 57%. The item variance values are as follows: X1: 100%, X2: 57.3%, X3: 61.2%, Z: 61.4% AND Y: 58.5%.

The next test is the Discriminant Validity test. A variable must be theoretically and statistically distinct from other variables, which can be assessed through the discriminant validity test. This test is performed by examining the cross-loading values and the Fornell-Larcker table. The Fornell-Larcker criterion explains that a latent variable should have a higher variance correlation with its own indicators than with other variables at the construct level. Meanwhile, cross-loading analysis evaluates validity at the indicator level (Ghozali, 2017).

The following presents the results of the Fornell-Larcker Criterion and Cross-Loading tests obtained using the PLS Algorithm:

Table 2. Value Fornell Larcker Criterion

	X1	X2	X3	Z	Y
X1	0,765				
X2	0,312	0,784			
X3	0,307	0,259	0,784		
Z	0,429	0,243	0,172	1,000	
Y	0,305	0,154	0,476	0,180	0,757

From Table 2, it can be seen that the first stage of testing in discriminant validity is the Fornell-Larcker criterion. The correlation between a variable and its indicators must be higher than its correlation with other variables. Based on the statistical test results using SmartPLS, it is known that the Locus of Control (X1) variable has a stronger correlation with its own indicators compared to the variables Management Information System (X2), Compliance (X3), Risk-Based Audit (Z), and Financial Governance (Y), with a correlation value of 0.765.

Furthermore, the Management Information System (X2) variable shows a higher correlation with its own indicators compared to other items, with a value of 0.784. The Compliance (X3) variable also has a higher correlation with its indicators compared to other variables, with a value of 0.784. Lastly, the Risk-Based Audit (Z) variable shows a higher correlation with its own indicators compared to the Financial Governance (Y) variable, with a correlation value of 1.000.

Table 3. Cross Loading Value

	X1	X2	X3	Z	Y
X1.1	1,000	0,358	0,29	0,232	0,379
X2.1	0,048	0,658	0,444	0,299	0,508
X2.2	0,114	0,788	0,441	0,329	0,48
X2.3	0,166	0,826	0,517	0,391	0,514
X2.4	0,209	0,799	0,532	0,383	0,417
X2.5	0,105	0,698	0,436	0,387	0,343
X3.1	0,093	0,343	0,639	0,358	0,351
X3.2	0,206	0,358	0,734	0,305	0,396
X3.3	0,113	0,414	0,850	0,4	0,379
X3.4	0,137	0,389	0,882	0,407	0,386
Z1	0,354	0,229	0,209	0,802	0,526
Z4	0,372	0,285	0,263	0,821	0,54
Z6	0,264	0,147	0,148	0,724	0,373
Y1	0,276	0,196	0,199	0,249	0,745
Y3	0,354	0,284	0,327	0,217	0,818
Y4	0,188	0,144	0,176	0,344	0,750
Y6	0,209	0,113	0,246	0,352	0,748
Y9	0,172	0,102	0,186	0,118	0,762

From Table 3, it can be seen that the second stage of discriminant validity testing is Cross Loading. Cross loading is the evaluation of discriminant validity at the item level, where each measured item must have a higher correlation with its corresponding construct than with other constructs.

Based on the data obtained, it is known that each measured item has a higher loading value on its intended construct compared to other constructs. For example, in the X1.1 column, the loading value for Locus of Control (X1) is 1.000, while the values for Management Information System (X2), Compliance (X3), Risk-Based Audit (Z), and Financial Governance (Y) are 0.358, 0.290, 0.232, and 0.379, respectively. This indicates

that the indicator or item $X1.1 > X2, X3, Z,$ and Y . The same applies to all items from $X2.1$ to $Y9$.

The columns $X1.1$ to $Y9$ represent the indicators being tested, while the columns $X1, X2, X3, Z,$ and Y at the top represent the corresponding variable values for each tested indicator. Therefore, after reviewing all cross-loading values for each indicator, it can be concluded that all indicators have passed the cross-loading test.

The evaluation of the inner structural model is conducted to determine the fit and strength of the relationships within the model. This evaluation involves several stages, namely examining the f-square, r-square, SRMR, and q-square values (Zakiah, 2017). The detailed explanation is as follows:

F-Square

The F-square test is conducted to assess the influence of variables at the structural level. The F-square value is categorized into three levels: a value of 0.02 indicates a small effect, 0.15 indicates a moderate effect, and 0.35 indicates a large effect (Hair et al., 2021). The following table presents the F-square values for each variable:

Table 4. F-squiare Valuei

Variabe l	F-Square
X1	0,125
X2	0,027
X3	0,016
Z	0,040

From Table 4, it can be seen that the Locus of Control (X1) variable has an f-square value close to the moderate category but is still considered low, with a value of 0.125. As previously explained, an f-square value is categorized as moderate if it is greater than 0.15. Meanwhile, the Management Information System (X2), Compliance (X3), and Risk-Based Audit (Z) variables have f-square values of 0.027, 0.016, and 0.040, respectively. Therefore, it can be concluded that Locus of Control (X1), Management Information System (X2), Compliance (X3), and Risk-Based Audit (Z) have low influence within the structural model.

R-Square

The R-square test in this study was conducted using SmartPLS to determine the extent to which exogenous variables can explain the endogenous variable. An R-square value is considered strong if it is greater than 0.67, moderate if it is around 0.33, and weak if it is 0.19 (Ghozali and Latan, 2015, p. 78). The R-square values in this study are presented in the following table:

Table 5. R-Square Valuei

	R-Square
APDD	0.295

From Table 5, it is known that the R-Square value of the model for Locus of Control (X1), Management Information System (X2), Compliance (X3), and Risk-Based Audit (Z) as moderating variables is 0.295. An R-Square value of 0.295 falls within the approaching moderate category. Therefore, it can be concluded that Locus of Control (X1), Management Information System (X2), Compliance (X3), and Risk-Based Audit (Z) as moderating variables can explain their influence on Financial Governance (Y) by 29.5%, while the remaining 70.5% of Financial Governance (Y) is explained by other variables outside the model used in this study.

Q-Square

The Q-Square, also known as Predictive Relevance, is used to measure how well the observed values are reconstructed by the model and its parameter estimates — in other words, how well the model has predictive capability. This test is conducted using the blindfolding procedure (Ghozali & Latan, 2018). The Q-Square value is calculated using the following formula:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R^2)$$

Thus, the calculation result is as follows:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0,295) = 1 - 0,705 = 0,295$$

From the calculation above, the obtained Q-Square value is 0.295. Since the Q-Square value is greater than 0, it indicates that the model used in this study has predictive relevance.

Hyphothsesis Testing

The next step in evaluating the inner model is determining the significance level to assess the relationships between latent variables using the bootstrapping method (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). The level of significance can be identified from the p-value and t-statistic in the path coefficients table. For a two-tailed hypothesis test with a 95% confidence level ($\alpha = 5\%$), the t-statistic threshold is 1.96. If the t-statistic value is greater than 1.96, the hypothesis is accepted.

Alternatively, the p-value can also be used — if the p-value ≤ 0.05 , the hypothesis is accepted, while a p-value > 0.05 indicates rejection. Additionally, the direction and magnitude of the relationship between variables can be observed in the original sample column.

The researcher presents the results of the analysis of latent variables in table 6.

Table 6. Hypothesis Testing Analysis Results

	Original sampe l	T-Statistik	P-Valu e	Conclusion
$X1 \rightarrow Y$	0,310	5,627	0.000	Accepted
$X2 \rightarrow Y$	0,167	2,528	0.012	Accepted
$X3 \rightarrow Y$	0,123	1,536	0.125	Rejected
$X1*Z \rightarrow Y$	-0,072	1,036	0.300	Rejected
$X2*Z \rightarrow Y$	- 0,007	0,107	0.915	Rejected
$X3*Z \rightarrow Y$	0,069	1,265	0.206	Rejected

Figure 4. Path Coefficient

Based on Table 6 and Figure 4, the results of the hypothesis testing can be described as follows:

Hypothesis 1 states that Locus of Control has an effect on Financial Governance — this hypothesis is accepted. The p-value obtained is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, indicating a significant effect. In addition, the t-statistic value is 5.627, which is greater than 1.96 at a 95% confidence level ($\alpha = 0.05$), and the original sample value is 0.310 (positive). Therefore, Locus of Control has a positive and significant effect on Financial Governance.

Hypothesis 2 states that Management Information Systems have an effect on Financial Governance — this hypothesis is accepted. The p-value is 0.01 (< 0.05), the t-statistic is 2.528 (> 1.96), and the original sample value is 0.167 (positive). Thus, Management Information Systems have a significant positive effect on Financial Governance.

Hypothesis 3 states that Compliance has an effect on Financial Governance — this hypothesis is rejected. The original sample value is 0.123 (positive), but the p-value is

0.125 (> 0.05) and the t-statistic is 1.536 (< 1.96). Therefore, Compliance does not have a significant effect on Financial Governance.

Hypothesis 4 states that Risk-Based Audit moderates and strengthens the influence of Locus of Control on Financial Governance — this hypothesis is rejected. The p-value is 0.300 (> 0.05), the t-statistic is 1.036 (< 1.96), and the original sample value is -0.072, indicating a negative direction. This means Risk-Based Audit weakens the influence of Locus of Control on Financial Governance.

Hypothesis 5 states that Risk-Based Audit moderates and strengthens the influence of Management Information Systems on Financial Governance — this hypothesis is rejected. The p-value is 0.915 (> 0.05), the t-statistic is 0.107 (< 1.96), and the original sample value is -0.007, meaning the moderating effect is negative and weakens the relationship between Management Information Systems and Financial Governance.

Hypothesis 6 states that Risk-Based Audit moderates and strengthens the influence of Compliance on Financial Governance — this hypothesis is rejected. The original sample value is 0.069 (positive), but the p-value is 0.206 (> 0.05) and the t-statistic is 1.265 (< 1.96). Thus, Risk-Based Audit does not moderate the effect of Compliance on Financial Governance.

Moderating Effect Test

In this study, the moderating variable used is the Risk-Based Audit, which moderates the relationships between Locus of Control, Management Information Systems, and Compliance on Financial Governance. The analysis of moderating effects can be seen in the original sample table. According to Priharto (2022), moderation effects are divided into four types:

1. Pure Moderation – occurs when the independent variables (Locus of Control, Management Information Systems, and Compliance) have no significant effect on Financial Governance, but after including the moderating variable (Risk-Based Audit), the effect becomes significant.

2. Quasi Moderation – occurs when the independent variables have a significant effect on Financial Governance, and the relationship remains significant after the moderating variable is added.

3. Homologizer Moderation – occurs when the independent variables have no significant effect on Financial Governance, and after including the moderating variable, the relationship remains insignificant.

4. Predictor Moderation – occurs when the independent variables significantly affect Financial Governance, but after adding the moderating variable, the effect becomes insignificant.

According to Jannah et al. (2018), the interpretation of moderating effects is categorized as small, medium, or large. A moderating effect is considered small when the value falls around 0.005, medium when it is around 0.01, and large when it reaches 0.025.

These values can be observed from the f-square results of the moderation analysis. Based on this explanation, the results of the moderating effects are presented for the influence of Locus of Control on Financial Governance, Management Information Systems on Financial Governance, and Compliance on Financial Governance, with Risk-Based Audit serving as the moderating variable.

Table 7. Moderation Effect

	P-Value	F-square	Description	Conclusion
X1 → Y	0.000	0.040	Significant	Pre dictor Mode ration
X1*Z → Y	0.300	(High)	Not Significant	
X2 → Y	0.012	0.000	Significant	Pre dictor Mode ration
X2*Z → Y	0.915	(Low)	Not Significant	
X3 → Y	0.125	0.005	Not Significant	Homologise r moderation
X3*Z → Y	0.206	(Low)	Not Significant	

From Table 7, it can be seen that the p-value of Locus of Control on Financial Governance is $0.000 < 0.05$, indicating a significant effect. Meanwhile, after being moderated by Risk-Based Audit, the p-value for Locus of Control on Financial Governance becomes $0.300 > 0.05$, meaning it is not significant. Therefore, Risk-Based Audit moderating Locus of Control on Financial Governance is categorized as a predictor moderation. This is because before the moderation, Locus of Control had a significant effect, but after being moderated by Risk-Based Audit, the effect became insignificant. The moderation effect is considered strong, with a value of 0.040, which is above 0.025.

Next, the p-value of Management Information Systems on Financial Governance is $0.000 < 0.05$, indicating a significant effect. However, after being moderated by Risk-Based Audit, the p-value increases to $0.300 > 0.05$, which means it becomes not significant. Hence, Risk-Based Audit moderating Management Information Systems on Financial Governance is also classified as a predictor moderation. This occurs because Management Information Systems had a significant effect before moderation but lost its significance afterward. The moderation effect is small, with a value of 0.000, which is below 0.005.

Furthermore, regarding Compliance on Financial Governance, both before and after being moderated by Risk-Based Audit, there is no significant effect. The p-value before moderation is $0.125 > 0.05$, and after moderation, it remains above 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that Risk-Based Audit does not moderate the effect of Compliance on Financial Governance, meaning this relationship falls under homologiser moderation. The f-square value for Risk-Based Audit moderating Compliance is 0.005, which indicates a small moderating effect.

The results of the outer model, as previously described, show that all variable indicators are valid, as they have loading values above 0.70. These results also confirm that the relevant indicators accurately reflect each variable in the study.

The Effect of Locus of Control on Financial Governance

The belief that an individual can influence events in their life is known as Locus of Control (Ladjamudin, 2021). Internal Locus of Control indicators include ability, interest, and effort, while external indicators include fate, luck, socioeconomic status, and the influence of others. Hence, Locus of Control is essential because it represents an individual's belief in whether they themselves or external factors control the events in their life.

Based on hypothesis testing results, the influence of Locus of Control on Financial Governance shows a positive value of 0.310 with a t-statistic of 5.627, which is higher than 1.96, and a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. It can thus be concluded that Locus of Control has a positive and significant effect on Financial Governance. This means that the stronger a person's Locus of Control, the better their financial governance will be.

In establishing good financial governance, the Locus of Control element plays an important role. To maintain consistent financial management, individuals must be able to control their financial behavior. Financial behavior is considered good when it contributes to one's financial well-being (Baker & Garland E. Allen, 2013). A healthy financial mindset includes avoiding the use of money to control others, solving problems wisely, and understanding that money should be managed and invested properly rather than merely saved (Indrawati, 2013).

These findings are supported by research from (Gusman & Auliffi, 2023), which found that Locus of Control significantly affects audit quality. Auditors at public accounting firms in Central Jakarta tend to have an internal Locus of Control, meaning they believe their skills, interests, and efforts determine their results. An auditor with an internal Locus of Control is generally more motivated in completing tasks. For example, when an employee disagrees with their supervisor, they are likely to make constructive suggestions to improve audit quality. Similarly, Priharta (2022) stated that auditors with a strong Locus of Control can regulate their actions despite external stimuli, maintaining objectivity and integrity. Such auditors are less easily influenced by others and uphold independence and skepticism, both of which are essential for protecting the public interest.

The findings are consistent with the research conducted by Ardiana & Aini (2022) and Setiawan (2022), which show that Locus of Control has a positive and significant influence on audit quality. Therefore, an increase in Locus of Control can lead to an improvement in audit quality. Auditors who are able to assess situations effectively tend to demonstrate better performance. Moreover, with a strong Locus of Control, motivation can be managed alongside stress control.

The Effect of Management Information Systems on Financial Governance

A Management Information System (MIS) is one of the organizational resources used to support decision-making processes at various management levels. Data can be processed into information according to the needs of managers at the lower, middle, and upper management levels. To ensure that the information meets managerial needs, a well-

designed MIS must be developed so that it can effectively support decision-making. Thus, evaluation is necessary to determine how well an implemented system functions in practice.

Within a management information system, there is always the possibility of errors or misuse, whether intentional or unintentional, and whether due to human error or system faults. Such errors or misuse can have a significant impact on a company's performance and operations, potentially causing losses in terms of materials, time, or effort. Therefore, it is essential to conduct evaluations and audits periodically—both on the information system itself and on its users and managers.

Based on the hypothesis testing results, the effect of Management Information Systems on Financial Governance shows a positive value of 0.167, with a t-statistic of 2.528, which is above 1.96, and a p-value of $0.012 < 0.05$. It can be concluded that the Management Information System variable has a positive and significant effect on Financial Governance. This means that the better the management and utilization of the information system, the greater the improvement in financial governance.

A Management Information System represents the use of information technology aimed at enhancing transparency, accountability, and financial governance. MIS can generate more accurate and reliable information compared to manual data processing and can help leaders make data-driven decisions. The existence of such a system is expected to assist individuals in managing financial activities, improve financial governance, and enhance overall organizational performance.

These findings are supported by research conducted by Robbins & Judge, (2018), who concluded that the use of information technology has a positive impact on organizational performance. The results are also in line with studies by Muranda (2006), which found that the implementation of SIMDA (Regional Management Information System) helps improve the quality of regional financial management, thereby increasing budget accuracy and performance.

The Effect of Compliance on Financial Governance

Compliance is related to a person's reputation or prestige in the eyes of others. People who see themselves as generous may feel embarrassed if they refuse to help when asked by others. According to Jane Neilson, the best way to encourage someone who behaves inappropriately is to provide positive motivation that encourages appropriate (good) behavior. When discouraging factors are eliminated, the motivation to act inappropriately tends to disappear naturally.

An individual's behavior is always influenced by internal and external factors. External factors originate from outside the person, while internal factors come from within the individual. Such influences are inevitable because they are part of the learning process. In corporate governance, compliance refers to adhering to specific specifications, standards, or laws clearly established by an authorized institution or organization in a given field.

Based on the hypothesis testing results, the effect of Compliance on Financial Governance shows a positive value of 0.123, with a t-statistic of 1.536, which is below 1.96, and a p-value of $0.125 > 0.05$. Therefore, it can be concluded that the Compliance variable has no significant effect on Financial Governance. This means that individuals with a high level of compliance do not necessarily contribute to improvements in financial governance.

These findings differ from the research by Altman et al (2019) titled “Analysis of Factors Affecting the Quality of Financial Reporting,” which found that compliance with government accounting standards has a positive effect on the quality of financial statements. Hence, Hypothesis 3 (H3), which proposed that compliance positively influences financial governance, is not supported.

The Effect of Locus of Control Moderated by Risk-Based Audit on Financial Governance

The implementation of Risk-Based Auditing (RBA) directs the planning and execution of audit activities to focus on areas or components with potential risk sources, thereby producing higher-quality audit reports. A risk-based audit is an auditing approach that relies on the results of an organization’s risk management process—including risk identification and analysis—which aims to identify factors that might hinder the organization in achieving its objectives.

Based on the results of the hypothesis testing, the risk-based audit variable moderating the effect of Locus of Control on Financial Governance shows a negative value of -0.072, with a t-statistic of 1.036, which is below 1.96, and a p-value of 0.300, which is greater than 0.05. It can thus be concluded that the risk-based audit variable is unable to moderate the effect of Locus of Control on Financial Governance. This means that an individual’s Locus of Control, when supported by the implementation of a risk-based audit, does not have any significant influence on Financial Governance.

This finding suggests that the risk-based audit method does not strengthen the effect of Locus of Control on Financial Governance. This result contradicts Attribution Theory, which states that an individual’s behavior is influenced not only by internal factors but also by external factors originating from outside the individual. The implementation of a risk-based audit represents one of the external attributions for auditors that can influence their actions or behavior during the auditing process. This audit method helps auditors gain a deeper understanding of the auditee’s condition, especially regarding high-risk activities or functions. Consequently, it should improve audit quality and support the achievement of better governance practices.

However, this result is not consistent with the findings of Setiawan (2022) which demonstrated that risk-based auditing can moderate the effect of auditor competence on audit quality, showing a strengthening effect.

The Effect of Management Information Systems Moderated by Risk-Based Audit on Financial Governance

Management Information Systems (MIS) must be continuously monitored and controlled to prevent the loss of company assets, theft, or abuse of authority that could cause harm to an organization. According to Castanheira et al (2010), internal irregularities typically arise due to three conditions:

Pressure/Incentive, where employees or departments are under pressure to meet certain goals set by higher management;

Opportunity, which allows misconduct to occur; and Attitude/Rationalization, which relates to ethical values and integrity, particularly within top management.

Integrity and ethical values are key elements of the control environment that influence the design, implementation, and monitoring of other control components. Strong integrity plays a crucial role in maintaining an effective internal control environment.

Risk represents the probability of an event occurring that could affect organizational objectives, combining both the impact and likelihood of occurrence. Risk-based auditing is part of the risk management process, which includes identifying, analyzing, and assessing risks. The implementation of risk management must be supported by appropriate management and control procedures. In healthcare centers (puskesmas), risk management can be conducted through four key steps: identifying, monitoring, tracking, and controlling risks.

The advantages of risk-based auditing include improving shareholder value, creating a strong risk management infrastructure, and enhancing an organization's competitiveness.

Based on the hypothesis testing results, the risk-based audit variable does not moderate the effect of Management Information Systems on Financial Governance, as indicated by a negative value of -0.007, a t-statistic of 0.107, which is below 1.96, and a p-value of 0.915, which is greater than 0.05. This means that Management Information Systems supported by risk-based audits do not significantly influence Financial Governance.

This result indicates that Hypothesis 5 (H5) is rejected. The p-value shows that while the interaction between risk-based audit and Management Information Systems may exist, the direction of the effect is negative, implying that risk-based auditing actually weakens the influence of Management Information Systems on Financial Governance.

This finding contradicts the research of Wawerui & Prot (2018), titled "The Effect of Auditor Competence and Independence on Audit Quality with the Implementation of Risk-Based Auditing as a Moderating Variable," which proved that the application of risk-based auditing strengthens the relationship between auditor competence and audit quality.

The Effect of Compliance Moderated by Risk-Based Audit on Financial Governance

An individual's attitude is always influenced by internal and external factors. External factors originate from outside the individual, while internal factors come from within. Such influences are inevitable because they form part of the learning process that shapes behavior. In corporate governance, compliance refers to adherence to specifications, standards, or regulations clearly established by an authorized institution or organization in a given field.

The implementation of good governance in public administration aims to accelerate societal welfare. According to Mawanza et al (2018) the goal of good governance is to create a solid and responsible administration carried out effectively and efficiently, while maintaining synergistic and constructive interactions among the state, private sector, and society. The utilization of resources must therefore consider both efficiency and effectiveness in achieving national objectives.

Thus, it is necessary to apply an audit method capable of directing the limited available resources directly toward risk centers that may hinder the achievement of regional development goals. This method is known as Risk-Based Auditing, as explained by David Galloway, IIA (2004) in Maune, (2015):

“Risk-Based Auditing is auditing in which audit objectives and audit planning are driven by a risk assessment philosophy.” Risk-Based Auditing is an audit approach based on the identification and evaluation of material risks that have the potential to obstruct the achievement of business objectives. Through this approach, the audit plan becomes more focused and well-directed, and the audit execution is concentrated on the sources of key issues, resulting in a higher-quality audit report.

Based on the hypothesis testing results, the risk-based audit variable does not moderate the effect of compliance on financial governance, as indicated by a positive coefficient of 0.069, a t-statistic value of 1.265 (below 1.96), and a p-value of 0.206 (greater than 0.05). Therefore, it can be concluded that the risk-based audit variable is unable to moderate the relationship between compliance and financial governance. This means that an individual's compliance, even when supported by a good risk-based audit system, does not significantly affect financial governance.

These findings are not consistent with the research of Setiawan (2022) titled “The Effect of Auditor Competence and Independence on Audit Quality with the Implementation of Risk-Based Auditing as a Moderating Variable.” The study concluded that auditor competence and independence have a positive and significant effect on audit quality. The application of risk-based auditing strengthens the relationship between auditor competence and audit quality, as well as the correlation between auditor independence and audit quality.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the overall data analysis in this study, several conclusions can be drawn as follows:

The influence of Locus of Control on Financial Governance shows a positive coefficient of 0.310, a t-statistic of 5.627 (above 1.96), and a p-value of 0.000 (less than 0.05). It can be concluded that Locus of Control has a positive and significant effect on Financial Governance. This means that the better an individual's Locus of Control, the better their contribution to improving Financial Governance. The influence of the Management Information System on Financial Governance shows a positive coefficient of 0.167, a t-statistic of 2.528 (above 1.96), and a p-value of 0.012 (less than 0.05). Thus, the Management Information System has a positive and significant effect on Financial Governance, indicating that better management of the information system leads to improved financial governance.

The influence of Compliance on Financial Governance shows a positive coefficient of 0.123, a t-statistic of 1.536 (below 1.96), and a p-value of 0.125 (greater than 0.05). Therefore, Compliance has no significant effect on Financial Governance. This means that a high level of compliance does not necessarily enhance financial governance. The Risk-Based Audit variable moderating the effect of Locus of Control on Financial Governance shows a negative coefficient of -0.072, a t-statistic of 1.036 (below 1.96), and a p-value of 0.300 (greater than 0.05). Thus, the Risk-Based Audit does not moderate the relationship between Locus of Control and Financial Governance, meaning that even when supported by a risk-based audit, Locus of Control does not significantly affect financial governance.

The Risk-Based Audit variable moderating the effect of the Management Information System on Financial Governance shows a negative coefficient of -0.007, a t-statistic of 0.107 (below 1.96), and a p-value of 0.915 (greater than 0.05). Hence, it can be concluded that Risk-Based Audit does not moderate the effect of the Management Information System on Financial Governance, implying that even with risk-based audit support, the management information system does not significantly influence financial governance. The Risk-Based Audit variable moderating the effect of Compliance on Financial Governance shows a positive coefficient of 0.069, a t-statistic of 1.265 (below 1.96), and a p-value of 0.206 (greater than 0.05). It can be concluded that Risk-Based Audit does not moderate the effect of Compliance on Financial Governance. This means that even when supported by an effective risk-based audit system, individual compliance does not significantly affect financial governance.

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<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Pituringasih, E., Sokarina, A., Handajani, L., Asmony, T. and Fitriani, B. T. (2026). Determinants of Financial Governance with Risk-Based Audit as a Moderating Variable at Community Health Centers Across Lombok Island. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 13(2), 192-218. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2026.551879.1875</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_239083.html</p>	A square QR code located in the bottom right corner of the 'HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE' section.